

Secondary School Wash Programme in Resource Scarce Communities of Developing Countries: A Systematic Review

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Abstract: Global research increasingly links improved access to secondary school WASH facilities with better student health and educational outcomes. This review examines underprivileged secondary school WASH programmes, their emotional impact on students' health, and how the adequacy of WASH infrastructure affects educational outcomes. The systematic research methodology was adopted from the Purssel and McCrae (2020) to select articles under consideration. The principal search acknowledged 2,262 publications whose titles discussed water supply and quality, sanitation infrastructures, hygiene including menstrual, and toilet infrastructures in secondary schools. Most of these references were obtained from scientific databases (n = 2221), with the majority from PubMed (n = 1030), Scopus (n = 352) and Google Scholar (n = 880) respectively. The result indicates that adequate WASH programmes and activities including menstrual hygiene and infrastructure exercises good health promotion among students with significant influence on educational output positively whereas insufficient and inadequate WASH infrastructure in secondary schools impede students to practice healthy hygiene behaviours across countries under review. In most countries, inadequate toilet and hygiene facilities have had significant negative effects on secondary school students.

Key words: Water sanitation, and hygiene (WASH), Scarce resources, community, Secondary schools, systematic review.

Introduction

Water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) are essential indispensable components of man daily needs. In public space, WASH is a fundamental educational right of the secondary school child and not a privilege (UN, 2015; Mooujinan, 2012; Humme, 2012). Children in secondary school need quality water and sanitation infrastructures because they spent a significant portion of their day at school, and where such services are made available, it impacts positive on learning, health, and dignity, most especially for the girl child and the physically challenged student (UNICEF, 2024). The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) Target 6.1 ensures equitable universal and affordable safe drinking water by 2030 (SDG, 2017). In same way, Target 6.2 emphasizes gaining access to satisfactory and evenhanded

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sanitation and hygiene for all, end open defecation (OD), and also to pay special attention to the needs of women and girls including those vulnerable situations. To achieve the SDGs, inadequate drinking water supply, unclean environment, and paucity of sanitation infrastructures have played a major significant hindrance (Sharma et al., 2022). More so, SDG Target 4a and other ancillary represent increasing recognition of their importance as key components of a safe, non-violent inclusive and effective learning environment and as part of universal WASH access, with emphases on the need for WASH outside the home (UNICEF, 2024; Nowreen, et al., 2022, Otto, 2022). However, one-third (31%) of schools worldwide do not have appropriate water supply and about 44% do not have proper sanitation (WHO/UNICEF, 2015).

Furthermore, studies have revealed that secondary school children of age bracket 5-14years are the most vulnerable group, and thus, exercises increased risk of disease transmission (Otto et al., 2022; WaterAid, 2018; WHO/UNICEF, 2015; UNICEF 1998). This age group is critical because children in this age group are still developing their hygiene habits, and thus may not fully understand the significance of proper WASH practices. Children immune system is still developing making them to be more susceptible to water borne and sanitation related illnesses (Bick et al., 2024). Globally, 88% of diarrhea giving rise to 1.5 million unnecessary deaths each year, particularly among developing countries due to deficiency in water, sanitation and hygiene practices (Pruss-Ustun et al., 2014) occur where poor knowledge and practice of WASH have been well documented (Egbiola & Amanambu, 2015, Olukaniri et al., 2014). Again, the physically challenged is reportedly having an increased risk of inadequate access to WASH infrastructure. About 15% of people worldwide have physical disabilities (White et al., 2016), underscoring the need for better WASH systems to help meet the Sustainable Development Goals. Accordingly, WHO (2010) averred that most secondary schools around the world lack water, sanitation, and hygiene infrastructures. In 2016, it was reported that 69% of schools worldwide had a basic drinking water services basic drinking water service, 12% had a limited drinking water service (i.e., no access to drinking water within 30 minutes of water collection). However, 19% of these schools did not even have a supply of drinking water (WHO/UNICEF, 2018).

In sub-Saharan Africa, a third of secondary schools lack toilets, and less than half ($\frac{1}{2}$) have sanitation infrastructures while 335 million girls worldwide attended secondary schools without essentials to ensure menstrual hygiene (WHO/UNICEF, 2018). WASH sector in schools should cater for the physically challenged and the girl child (mostly menstrual hygiene management (MHM) (WBG, 2022; Gensech & Tillet, 2019; Erhard et al., 2013). Good menstrual hygiene management (MHM) exhibits a fundamental role in empowering women, girls, and other menstruates to reach their full potential. The adverse effects of inadequate menstrual health and hygiene are multi-sectorial, and the challenges encountered by menstruating girls, women, and others extend beyond mere shortages of supplies or infrastructure (WBG, 2022; McMichael, 2019).

In Nigeria, community approaches and practices have evolved under the FGN-UNICEF WASH Programmes. The “Promising Practices” is a follow-up to the previous compendium of case studies in 2014 highlighting best practices in Community Led Total Sanitation interventions across Nigeria (Akpabio, 2012). Albeit, 87% (179 million) Nigerians do not have access to safely manage drinking water scenario. Most of the citizen lacks effective sanitation and hygiene practices. More so, literature holds that secondary schools' students have good knowledge on WASH but this does not translate to their practical knowledge of WASH (Otto et al., 2022; Ikegulu et al., (2024). The poorest households with only 2% access are 17 times less likely to have access to safely managed water services compared to the richest household with 37% access (FMWR/ NBS/WB/UNICEF, 2022; FMWR/UNICEF, 2007). The Vision 20:2020 of 2009 recognized WASH as a priority sector and set targets for 100% access to WASH activities by 2020, and to end open defecation by 2025 (FMWR, 2016), Strategies to attain SDGs that focuses on eliminating inequalities in WASH access (WHO/UNICEF, 2021) include the National School Health Policy (NSHP) among others. Despite due diligence, there is no proper action plan to demonstrate WASH programme in secondary school pragmatically as posited by Alawode &

Awafeso (2018), and Ikegulu et al, (2024). Thus, huge gap exists between the theory of WASH activities in secondary schools due to paucity of water supply, toilet and other sanitary infrastructures, poor knowledge of the perceived impact of hygiene behaviour of secondary school students' overall well-being. Therefore, the review aims at describing the need for increasing WASH activities in secondary schools. Furthermore, the review examines underprivileged secondary school WASH programmes, their emotional impact on students' health, and how the adequacy of WASH infrastructure affects educational outcomes.

Methodology

This study adopts the systematic research method developed by Purssel and McCrae (2020) to select articles for consideration. Peer-reviewed literature was systematically reviewed using PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar. The article based on the impact of WASH programmes and their deficiencies, paucity and impact on secondary school students' health and educational output especially for secondary schools in underprivileged communities were considered. These impacts contain an increase or decrease in secondary school attendance, secondary school dropout, or any type of physical, social, or psychological illness. The review was delimited to studies that explicitly see the sights of the effects of the provision or absence of water, sanitation, and related hygiene materials such as soap, towels, water sources, and toilet infrastructures in the secondary school in underprivileged communities.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Articles with WASH, secondary school students' health status, secondary school attendance with regularity, educational achievement, water sources, hand washing and toilet infrastructure were the focus of this study. The review examined both health and educational outcomes. The health effects considered in the study covered social, mental, and physical health topics as outlined by the National Institute of Health. Educational included attendance and academic performance. The intervention is defined as the provision of water, a wash hand basin, soap, and drying devices, or facilities for drinking, sanitation and hygiene (UNICEF, n.d.; UNICEF, 2014). Studies only on the impact of availability of sanitary napkins and impact of fluoride in drinking water were excluded. Sanitation was defined based on the availability of facilities to urinate or defecate either as private, safe toilets, latrines, including availability of toilet papers or potable water for cleaning and flushing or as facilities for women and girls to manage menstruation (i.e., secrete location and means for management and or disposal of menstrual hygiene materials including hand sanitizers were included. The researchers considered "water" as having the following attributes: availability, accessibility, affordability, and acceptability for drinking, hand-washing and cleaning.

Search Strategy for the Identification of Studies

A systematic literature research strategy was adopted which convoluted the use of different database to identify and review journal articles. PubMed, Google Scholar, Scopus, and Science Direct were searched in November and December 2024. In January 2025, a follow-up probe for successive published work was conducted and two (2) articles that met the inclusion criteria were added to the review. The primary search was based on key words: Secondary schools, scarce resources, Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene Management, Mensuration and Water or Sanitation, Toilet infrastructure and Water, secondary School Health Policies and Water or Sanitation, Secondary Schools Health, and WASH (Water, Sanitation and Hygiene). All citations were properly referenced. All in-text citation was properly referenced. The study was circumscribed to documents for which an abstract and articles in English was available. There was no restriction in time or location. Studies not written in English, or without an available English translation, were excluded from the review.

Inclusion, Exclusion and Yielded Phase

The principal search acknowledged 2,262 publications whose titles discussed water supply and quality, sanitation

infrastructures, hygiene including menstrual, and toilet infrastructures in secondary schools. A total of 2,221 references were collected from scientific databases, with 1,030 sourced from PubMed. Furthermore, the secondary screenings based on abstract identified 842 relevant references. Sixty-five (65) articles were assessed for eligibility, and thirty-three (33) articles met the inclusion criteria for full-text review. Some studies were excluded for the following reasons: 1. Articles that were not original studies but are rather reviews (n = 5), 2. Studies that were not related to secondary schools or education (n = 3), 3. Studies that were not deepened in WASH (n = 2) and 4. Studies that exercise no health impact (n = 2). Finally, 21 articles were included in the systematic review. An additional four (4) studies were included following the initial review, resulting in a total of twenty-five (25) studies utilized in the data analysis (n = 25) (see Figure 1; Table 3).

Results

Article was summarized based on the researcher, topic, country, study design, and principal findings. Since the study employs divers' methods and outcome measure, no attempt was employed to weigh the value of findings because of the quality of the study. Out of the 25 (100%) articles, 4(16%) reported the impact of diarrheal and other hygiene related diseases in schools, 5(20%) reported changes in WASH Knowledge and Hygiene behaviour and students, 3(12%) reported on intervention fidelity or conformity, 3(12%) reported on menstrual hygiene management (MHM), 5(20%) reported on students in Absenteeism while 3(12%) reported on WASH and sanitation in schools, and 2(8%) reported on WASH infrastructure in schools respectively (Table 1).

Figure1: PRISMA flow chart showing procedure for article selection. DCM = Duplicate copy removed, RMI = Record marked as ineligible, RRR = Retrieved for other reasons. Reason 1= Not Original Studies, Reason 2 = Studies not related to Secondary Schools, Reason 3 = Studies not deepened in WASH, Reason 4 = Studies with no health impact.

Table 1: Outcomes Measures Reported in included Articles (n=25)

Outcomes	%of studies	Studies
Impact of diarrheal and other hygiene related in secondary schools	4 (16%)	Bick et al., 2024, Sharma et al., 2022, Poague et al., 2022, WHO/UNICEF, 2022 .
Changes in WASH knowledge and hygiene behaviour among students	5 (20%)	Otto et al., 2022, Chard et al., 2018, Antwi-Agyei et al., 2017, Trinies et al., 2016., Freeman et al., 2014.
Intervention fidelity (Conformity)	3 (12%)	Norween et al., 2022, Chard et al., 2019, Mills et al., 2016.
Menstrual hygiene management in secondary school	3 (12%)	Poague et al., 2023, Mills et al., 2016, Seid et al., 2013,
Impact of WASH and students Absenteeism	5 (20%)	O'reelly et al., 2017, Jasper et al., 2012, Nlunda et al., 2013, Balogun-Adeleye et al., 2021, UNICEF, 2024.
WASH and sanitation in secondary schools	3 (12%)	Poague et al., 2023, Balongun et al., 2021, Alexander et al., 2018.
Toilet infrastructure in secondary schools	2 (8%)	Jordanavo et al., 2015, Freeman et al., 2015 .

Twelve (12) i.e., 48% studies reported outcome measures across more than one category (Egbinola et al., 2015, Poague et al., 2022, Chard et al., 2019, Norween et al., 2016, Poague et al., 2023, Trinies et al., 2016, Antwi-Agyei et al., 2017, Jasper et al., 2012, Freeman et al., 2014, Seid et al., 2013, Ana et al., 2008, Mills et al., 2016 respectively) (Table 3). The countries of focus included Nigeria, USA, Niger, Leo People Democratic Republic, Mali, India, Tanzania, Central America, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Kenya, Brazil and Netherland (Table 2).

Table 2: Countries of Focus

Name of Countries	Design used
Nigeria	Descriptive
USA	Descriptive/Systematic analysis
Niger	Systematic randomized sampling
Leo People Democratic Republic	Structured Questionnaire/interview method
Mali	Cluster randomized trial
India	Cluster randomized trial, method control trial
Tanzania	Participatory mixed method analysis
Central America	Participatory mixed method analysis
Democratic Republic of Congo	Descriptive cross-sectional approach
Ethiopia	Cross-sectional approach
Kenya	Quasi-randomized trial/descriptive survey
Brazil	Cluster randomized trial
Netherland	Systematic and meta-analysis

TABLE 3: Description of the 25 studies included in the Systematic Review

S/N	RESEARCHER	TOPIC	LOCATION	DESIGN	OUTCOMES
1	Egbinola et al., 2015	Water supply, sanitation and hygiene education in secondary schools in Ibadan	Ibadan, Nigeria	Systematic Random sampling	1. 24% use water closet, 2. 7 uses pit latrine. Out of 85%, 88% uses ordinary pit latrine while 12% used VIP latrine.
2	Balogun-Adeleye, et al., 2021	Water and sanitation facilities in secondary schools in Ibadan, South-west Nigeria.	Ibadan, Nigeria	Structured questionnaire and interview method	1. Deep tube-wells and pit latrines were widely used. 2. 70% of schools surveyed used traditional pit latrine while 73% had deep-tube wells. 3. There were very few hand washing facilities in the schools
3.	Sharma et al., 2022	School water, sanitation and hygiene: A systemic review of an effect on health, attendance, regularity, and educational achievement	Nepal South Asia	Systematic search strategy Pursell and McCrae (2020)	1. That intervention of school WASH facilities influences students' health status, regularity in school attendance, and educational achievement. 2. It helps protect students from infectious diseases linked to inadequate WASH access; however, proper management is just as crucial.
4	Jasper et al., 2012	Water and Sanitation in Schools: A Systematic Review of the Health and Educational Outcomes	USA	-	Studies documented female discomfort in the school environment during menses due to inadequacies in the assurance of privacy, disposal of materials for menstruation, or sufficient school
5	McMichael, C. 2019	Water, Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH) in Schools in Low - Income Countries: A Review of Evidence of Impact		Descriptive	Evidence of the impact of school-based WASH programs in reducing student absence from school was mixed.

6	Maïnassara et al., 2014	Assessing the Health Impact of the following Measures in Schools in Maradi (Niger): Construction of Latrines, Clean Water Supply, Establishment of Hand Washing Stations, and Health Education	Niger	Descriptive	A statistically significant reduction in cases of diarrhea and abdominal pains was noted after the project.
7	Chard et al. 2018	Design, Implementation Fidelity, and Outcomes of a School-Based WASH Program	Lao People's Democratic Republic	Cluster-Randomized Trial	Even among schools with the highest levels of fidelity and adherence, impact of the intervention on absence and health was minimal.
8	Chard et al., 2019	Design, Implementation Fidelity, and Outcomes of a School-Based WASH Programme	Lao People's Democratic Republic	Cluster-Randomized Trial	No impact of the WinS intervention on any primary (pupil absence) or secondary (enrollment, dropout, grade progression, diarrhea, respiratory infection, conjunctivitis, STH infection) impacts.
9.	Trinies et al., 2016	The Impact of a School-Based Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene Program on Absenteeism, Diarrhea, and Respiratory Infection	Mali	A Matched-Control Trial	School-based WASH intervention can have a positive effect on reducing rates of illness, as well as absence due to diarrhea.
10.	Nowreen et al., 2022	A participatory SWOT analysis on water, sanitation, and hygiene management of disabled females	Dhaka, Bangladesh	Participatory mixed method Analysis	Prohibitive costs of hygiene products are identified as primary challenges.
11.	Otto et al., 2022	Water, Sanitation and Hygiene Practice among Students in Secondary School, Ijebu Ode, Nigeria	Ijebu Ode, Ogun state, Nigeria	A descriptive cross-sectional approach	Majority of the students in Ijebu Ode have adequate knowledge (78.9%) and inadequate

12.	WHO/UNICEF, 2022	Progress on drinking water, sanitation and hygiene in schools: 2000-2021 Data update	-	-	3 in 10 schools or 29 per cent do not have a basic drinking water service, impacting 546 million, 3 in 10 schools or 28 per cent do not have basic sanitation services, impacting 539 million children schoolchildren, and 4 out of 10 or 42 per cent of schools do not have basic hygiene services, impacting 802 million children.
13	Mills et al., 2016	The impact of water, sanitation and hygiene on key health and social outcomes: Review of evidence.	-	-	One contributing factor is a lack of appropriate WASH facilities, without which many girls are likely to miss school while they menstruate.
14.	Antwi-Agyei et al., 2017	Water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) in schools: results from a process evaluation of the National Sanitation Campaign in Tanzania	Tanzania.	A cross-sectional study	53% of schools had a reliable water supply, 43% had some functional hand washing stations, but only 29% and 19% had water and soap available at the stations, respectively.
15.	Jordanova et al., 2015	Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene in Schools in Low Socio-Economic Regions in Nicaragua: A Cross-Sectional Survey	Nicaragua, Central America	A Cross-Sectional Survey	Presence of drinking water infrastructure (43%), sanitation infrastructure (64%), 81% had no hand washing stations and 74% of schools lacked soap, 28% of schools did not use sanitation facilities and 26% had no functional water system.

16.	Ndidi Egbinola, C. & Chukwudi Amanambu, A. (2015)	Water supply, sanitation, and hygiene education in secondary schools in Ibadan, Nigeria.	Ibadan, Nigeria	systematic random sampling	Twenty-four percent (24%) of schools used W/C while 76% of schools used pit toilets, 88% were ordinary pit toilets and 12% VIP. The number of toilets within the schools ranged between 0 and 14, revealing a 185:1 student to toilet ratio within the study area, but ranged widely from 83:1 to 510:1 between schools.
17.	Nlunda et al., 2025	Assessing School-Based Water, Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH) Facilities in Peri-Urban Settings of Kinshasa, DR Congo. Open Journal of Epidemiology	DR Congo	A cross-sectional study	43% of schools had hand-washing facilities
18.	Seid & Kumie, 2013	The status of school sanitation facilities in some selected primary and secondary schools	Ethiopia	Descriptive	The overall latrine to school population ratio was (1:64), The facility for female's toilets is far less than the male. Access to drinking water facilities (water taps) and hand washing facilities were very much limited to the extent not conforming to the standard.
19.	sl., 2014	Hygiene and health: systematic review of hand-washing practices worldwide and update of health effects.	Kenya	Quasi-randomized trials	Out of the 42 studies reporting hand-washing prevalence, approximately 19% of the world population washes hands with soap after contact with excreta
20.	Poague et al., 2023	Water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) in schools in Brazil pre-and peri-COVID-19 pandemic: Are schools making any progress?	Brazil		Results indicate that 9 million students in Brazil lack sanitation services in their schools. Comparison of WASH in schools pre- and peri-COVID-19 pandemic reveal little improvement.

21.	O'reilly et al., 2007	The impact of a school-based safe water and hygiene programme on knowledge and practices of students and their parents: Nyanza Province, western Kenya, 2006	Kenya	Survey	From 2004 to 2005, school absenteeism in the September–November term decreased in nine project schools by 35% and increased in nine neighbouring comparison schools by 5%.
22.	Ana et al., 2008	Water and sanitation problems in selected schools in Ibadan, Nigeria.	Ibadan, Nigeria	Descriptive cross-sectional survey	60% of the respondents use water in their various school premises. Majority 49(98%) especially at OAHs reported that the water was used mainly for cleaning in the school premises.
23.	Poague et al., 2022	Water, Sanitation and Hygiene in Schools in Low- and Middle-Income Countries: A Systematic Review and Implications for the COVID-19 Pandemic	Netherland	A mixed method of analysis	There were lack of adequate WASH conditions and menstrual hygiene management requirements in all countries. Insufficient and inadequate school infrastructure hampers students to practice healthy hygiene habits and hand-washing in particular
24.	Alexander et al., 2018	Do Water, Sanitation and Hygiene Conditions in Primary Schools Consistently Support Schoolgirls' Menstrual Needs? A Longitudinal Study in Rural Western Kenya	Kenya	Cluster randomized controlled pilot feasibility study	Soap availability for students increased significantly between baseline and follow-up while there was a significant decrease in the number of “acceptable” latrines.
25.	Bick et al., 2024	Impact of a school-based water and hygiene intervention on child health and school attendance in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia: a cluster- randomized controlled trial.	Addis Ababa, Ethiopia	cluster-randomized trial	There was 16% relative reduction in odds of pupil-reported respiratory illness in the past 7 days during follow-up in intervention vs. control schools (aOR 0.84;

Discussion

The main objective of this systematic review is to describe how Secondary School WASH programmes in underprivileged community of developing countries impact on students' health, and educational outcomes as well as ascertain the adequacy and effectiveness of WASH infrastructures on the students of these secondary schools. Water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) are fundamental components that are indispensable to the development and growth of the educational system mostly as it affects the students of secondary schools. Thus, it becomes a right and not a privilege to the students at this level of education (UNICEF, 2024; UN, 2015; Mooujina, 2012). From the study in Addis Ababa-Ethiopia, Kenya, Nigeria, and Mali, there were ebb and flow of school absenteeism between 2004 and 2005 (Bick et al., 2024, Alexander et al., 2018, Trinies et al., 2016, Ana et al., 2008, O'reilly et al., 2007). More so, 35% decrease in absenteeism and 5% increase in absenteeism especially in Kenya was recorded. The nexus for this observed changeability could be due to scarce resources to enhance WASH programmes in these underprivileged communities of developing countries. This corroborates with that of UNICEF (2024) and UN (2015), that paucity and poor WASH activities in schools exert negative influences on student health and behaviours especially in underprivileged communities of developing countries. Again, studies in this review indicated that changes in WASH knowledge and hygiene among secondary students is possible and plausible when school-based WASH interventions are put to practice pragmatically at all levels of implementations, and thus exercises 28% in the current study. The implication here is that increase WASH-related knowledge and practices improve educational outcomes of secondary students in addition to decreasing or reducing secondary students' absenteeism (WHO/UNICEF, 2022). This also corroborates the views of Trinies et al., 2016 in Mali and Otto et al., 2022 in Nigeria.

The deficiencies in the WASH programme in secondary schools located under-privileged communities have both implicit and explicit influence on both student health and hygiene status. Egbinola et al., 2015 in Nigeria, McMichael 2019 in Niger, Sharma et al., 2022 in Nepal (South Asia), Freeman et al., 2014 in Kenya and Poague et al., 2022 in Netherland in this review further demonstrated that diarrheal and associated hygiene related diseases influence secondary students output in terms of attendance and performances. Hand hygiene facilities and hygiene instructions improves attendance in public secondary schools mostly during the flu period. In Kenya, study exhibited strong association between secondary school WASH policies, health and attendance which invariably serves as datum for educational improvement of students. As a result, absenteeism among girls is often associated with insufficient menstrual hygiene management, as many secondary schools do not have adequate facilities. Secondly, cultural influence of menstruation in some countries studied hide under the jaw of poverty, lack of adequate knowledge on WASH practices and significance. Girls dropped out of secondary schools due to menstrual embarrassment at first instance in secondary school because of lack of prior preparation. In some quarters, absenteeism is up to 3-5 days per month. Sharma et al., (2022) maintained that at least three (3) days of absence per month is an ideal standard for the girls resulting from poor sanitary infrastructure at secondary school. Thus, the authors x-rayed strong connectivity between absenteeism, menstrual hygiene challenges (teasing, feeling distracted in class, physical discomfort among others), and ineptitude of adequate WASH infrastructure provision, sensitization and awareness creation, and its effective and efficient utilization in secondary schools by teachers and parents.

Potable drinking water, proper sanitation and effective hygiene practices are veritable tools in developing a healthy secondary schools' community. One indispensable determinant factor to achieving sustainable vibrant and healthy community among students in secondary schools is the recognition and application of WASH programmes (UNICEF, 2024; TSP, 2025). Water, sanitation and hygiene infrastructure in secondary schools includes toilet and hand-washing facilities, quality water sources: boreholes or tube wells, piped borne-water, protected hand-dug wells, protected springs, rainwater, packaged or delivered water (TSP, 2025; Ana et al., 2018; Antwi-Agyei et al., 2017; Norween et al., 2016; Jordanavo et al., 2015). In this review, WASH infrastructure in secondary schools had 44% representing 11 reviewed

articles cutting across Nigeria, Central America, Tanzania, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, and Kenya. Literature holds that in Netherland, during the Covid-19 saga, insufficient and inadequate secondary school infrastructure hampers students to practice healthy hygiene habits and hand-washing in particular. There were lack of adequate WASH conditions and menstrual hygiene management requirements in all countries (Poague et al., 2022). In Brazil, 9 million students lack sanitation services in their secondary school and in comparison, with WASH in schools pre- and peri-COVID-19 pandemic era revealed little improvement (Poague et al., 2023). In the Democratic Republic of Congo, only 10.9% of secondary schools had water points. The ratios of latrines units for girls were 58:1 for toilets and 115:1 for urinals, justifying open defecation and urination reported in 62.4% of schools. Forty-three percent of secondary schools had hand-washing facilities (Nlunda et al., 2025). This clearly demonstrates hygiene infrastructure deficiencies within the studied countries and could likely serve as risk to secondary student community. Elsewhere in Nigeria, 60% of the respondents use well water in their various secondary school premises. According to Ana et al. (2022), majority 49(98%) of respondents, particularly at OAHS, reported that water was primarily used for cleaning secondary school premises. A further study in Ibadan, Nigeria, revealed that 24% of secondary schools used water closet (W/C) while 76% of secondary schools used pit toilets, and out of this, 88% were ordinary pit toilets and 12% had ventilated improved pit-latrines (VIP). The number of toilets within the secondary schools ranged between 0 and 14 revealing a 185:1 student to toilet ratio within the study area, but ranged widely from 83:1 to 510:1 between schools. One contributing factor is a lack of appropriate WASH facilities, without which many girls are likely to miss school while they menstruate (Mills et al., 2016). This revelation is shocking as it highlights a significant infrastructure deficit. Lack of spontaneous government assistance or policy could probably be responsible for this observed absurdity. The findings in this study validated that of Ogbemudia (2021) in Rivers State, Nigeria, that school infrastructural decay exercises diverse effect on student community which could be as a result failed government policy and or paucity of governmental assistance.

CONCLUSION

Secondary school Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) programmes are essential for lowering disease risks among students at secondary school and home. WASH activities impact positively on secondary school students' health and educational outcomes whereas paucity of these WASH infrastructures causes deterioration of secondary students' health and their educational outcomes. The study suggested that WASH intervention serves as panacea in ameliorating the plight of the suffering secondary student's populace from increase absenteeism to decreased absenteeism thereby increasing student school regularity.

Recommendations

Consequently, the study recommends that WASH services including fixed hand-washing stations with running water, wholesome water supply, functional toilet facilities made with quality materials, and sanitation infrastructures should be made available and accessible to everyone in secondary schools. This will encourage the hygiene status of the students mostly the female gender. Secondary school population is large enough to produce enough waste (both solid and liquid waste). Poor waste management contributes to risk of infection. Thus, the researcher recommends that this area be incorporated for further study.

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